

Effects of principals' leadership styles on teachers' commitment in Vietnam

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 15, 2022

Revised Jun 15, 2023

Accepted Jul 7, 2023

Keywords:

Organizational commitment

School leadership

Transactional leadership

Transformational leadership

Vietnamese teachers

ABSTRACT

In recent years, styles of transformational and transactional leadership have become an important area of research because of its significant impact on teachers' outcomes such as commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy. However, the relationships between transformational and transactional leadership styles of school principals and teachers' organizational commitment have been rarely investigated in the educational context in Vietnam. This study aimed to determine how transformational and transactional leadership styles influence the organizational commitment of Vietnamese high school teachers. The study employed two standardized surveys to collect data from 387 teachers at 24 public high schools in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam. The results of correlation coefficient analyses indicated that teachers' organizational commitment was positively influenced by transformational leadership and negatively influenced by transactional leadership. In addition, the results of multiple regression analyses showed that the organizational commitment of teachers was predicted by all components of both leadership styles of principals. The present study suggested that school leaders might combine both transformational and transactional leadership styles in their leadership practices to improve teachers' organizational commitment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Leaders in Vietnamese public high schools have been adopting greater national changes as a result of increased demands on teacher results and educational quality [1]. Additional responsibilities for school administrators include developing strategic plans that improve school performance, motivating teachers and providing a favorable learning environment for student achievement [2]. Teacher morale and productivity, student achievement, and school effectiveness are all positively affected by school principals [3]–[5]. Recently, educational experts have paid more attention to two particular types of school principals' leadership, i.e. transformational leadership and transactional leadership [6]. Transformational leadership focuses on boosting employee happiness and motivation, while transactional leadership encourages employees' performance by rewarding and disciplining them for their actions [7]. Previous studies showed that transformational leadership increases the self-efficacy and organizational commitment of teachers, as

well as student achievement [8], [9]. Transformational and transactional leadership styles may, according to a growing corpus of research [10], significantly affect teachers' performance and organizational commitment. Despite increasing evidence in favor of these theories, research on the impacts of different leadership styles on teachers' professional commitment in educational situations in Vietnam is still sparse.

In the context of education in Vietnam, until now only a few studies have been conducted to investigate leadership styles of principals in schools. Research focuses on exploring the effects of transformational and transactional leadership on teachers' job satisfaction performance [1], the influences of social and cultural values on decision making of principals [6], and the application of transformational, transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles in higher education [11]. However, these studies have not explored the relationships between transformational and transactional leadership styles and teachers' organizational commitment in the context of high schools in Vietnam. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the effects of principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles on high school teachers' organizational commitment in Vietnam. The findings of the study will help school principals better understand the types of leadership styles that are most effective and how those styles impact the level of commitment among their teachers.

Leadership "is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal" [7] or "a process of leading or influencing others to achieve a desired goal" [10]. An effective leader is critical to the success of the organization's aims and aspirations. In different contexts, leaders may use a variety of different leadership styles and actions to help their teams achieve the common goals of the organization. In recent years, transformational and transactional leadership styles have attracted the attention of researchers because of their significant influences on teachers' outcomes.

Transformational leadership is "the engagement of one or more persons with others in such a way that leaders and followers raise one another to higher levels of motivation and morality" [12]. According to Bass and Riggio [13], transformational leaders work with their teams instead of doing all of the work on their own, and collaborate with others in order to achieve a common vision of the organization. The Full Range Model of Leadership [13] incorporates it as a crucial element based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs. Expanding Burn's research [12], Bass [14] identifies five transformational leadership dimensions which show that transformational leadership increases employee satisfaction and organizational commitment.

In this study, the following five components of transformational leadership were used as independent variables. Idealized influence attributed (IIa) describes a leader who is a great role model and is revered and respected by his or her followers. This component relates to the extent to which the leader may inspire pride in his or her followers for being members of the organization [10]. Idealized influence behavior (IIb) refers to the level of trust that a leader fosters among staff members in order to create a unified goal and vision for the organization [13]. A leader who shows this has high ethical standards and serves as a role model for his or her group [8]. Inspirational motivation (IM) refers to the extent to which a leader can effectively express a common vision of the organization's goals, inspire a sense of commitment from his followers to those goals, and communicate high expectations [13]. Intellectual stimulation (IS) refers to the extent to which a leader challenges the perspectives and guiding principles of their followers with regard to how to respond to difficult circumstances as well as how the leader involves their followers in the decision-making process and encourages them to find innovative solutions to problems [13]. Individualized consideration (IC) refers to how much of a leader's time, effort, and attention is devoted to creating a work environment for his or her subordinates, as well as cultivating future leaders by encouraging and supporting existing models [10].

Transactional leadership style is one in which the leader uses both rewards and penalties to encourage cooperation from their employees [12], and takes the decision without involving the group members [13]. In other words, transactional leadership is occurring when it involves an exchange of things of value between the leader and their followers. The Full Range Model of Leadership [13] is based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which emphasizes the degree to which fundamental needs are satisfied. Transactional leaders often offer rewards for effective work or good results and punishments for poor-quality work [8]. A transactional leader ensures that rules and processes are strictly adhered to, monitors work progress, and evaluates the effectiveness of individuals and groups within the organization. Thus, the staff of transactional leaders are not expected to have creativity, and they can be evaluated against established criteria [7].

There are four behavior dimensions of transactional leadership which show why this leadership style may not create supportive working environment [14]. These four elements of transactional leadership are recognized as independent variables in the research model for this study. Contingent reward (CR) refers to the leader who uses rewards to reinforce their staff's behaviors by using motivation or use punishments [7]. The way the leaders strengthen staff behavior by using motivation can simply be the way the leaders give praises to their staff. Leaders give praise when followers complete tasks on time or when followers accelerate task completion. In contrast, sometimes the leaders use punishments to control staff's misbehaviors when they delay or fail to achieve the set goals and take longer to complete tasks than expected [8]. Active

management by exception (AmbE) refers to the leader who only actively manages case-by-case, constantly checks on employee performance and gives recommendations for correction throughout monitoring these individuals [14]. These leaders expect their staff to follow the rules and principles, articulate ineffective behaviors, and often apply penalties for the lack of compliance with established standards.

Management by exception passive (MbEP) refers to the leader who intervenes only when something is wrong [7]. The leaders tend to avoid interfering with behaviors that should be avoided. They avoid making decisions, reacting to problems, concretizing agreements, clarifying expectations, and issuing performance standards to individuals. These leaders are only motivated to behave when mistakes become chronic. These leaders will often not intervene deeply until the problems become serious. Laissez-faire leadership (LF) refers to the leader who avoids interference. The leaders are often absent when important issues occur [7]. Bass [14] argues that it is rare for these leaders to take specific actions on the issues of need. This leadership style is considered as a “leaderless style” rather than a “transactional leadership style” [8].

Organizational commitment is often viewed as the respective strength of a person’s identification with and engagement in a specific organization or the connection of the employees to their organization, or “the psychological linkage between employees and their organizations” [15]. In other words, organizational commitment refers to the belief and willingness of an employee to serve the aims and values of the organization in order to become a long-term employee [16]. The three components of commitment are as: i) a sentimental desire to stay in the organization (affective commitment), which is generated mostly via work experiences that promote emotions of comfort and personal competence; ii) a need (continuance commitment) to stay in the organization, which emerges from the awareness of costs (e.g., the existence of side bets, the unavailability of alternatives) associated with leaving; and iii) an obligation (normative commitment) to the organization based on the loyalty norms or the receipt of favor which needs the repayments [17].

The three components of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment were identified as dependent variables in the present study. Affective commitment (AC) refers to the level of staff loyalty to the organization [15]. This concept is relative to staff who has a strong affective commitment to the organization due to their emotional attachment to it, identification with it, and participation in it [16]. Employees, with affective commitment, value the objectives of the organization, is more satisfied with their job, and believe that they are a good fit for it [18]. Continuance commitment (CC) is relative to the staffs’ need to stay in the organization [15]. It also referred to an awareness of the costs related to leaving the job, and staff with strong continuance commitment stay due to their wish to do so [16]. The fundamental reason for their commitment to the organization is because they feel compelled to do so. There is a variety of reasons for employees to stay with an organization. The most common ones have to do with job and pay. They fear losing these benefits if they leave the organization. Normative commitment (NC) refers to the extent to which employees feel obligated to stay in the organization [15]. Employees who have a strong sense of duty for their organization frequently believe that they are obligated to remain with the organization. Employees’ reasons for feeling this way vary, but many are concerned that leaving the organization would leave a void in its knowledge or abilities, which will put further strain on their remaining fellow employees [16].

Leadership styles have significant effects on employees’ commitment, which may lead to either the success or failure of an organization [19]. Transformational leadership has been widely researched and introduced as a result of changes in the education system [20]. Leaders that use a transformational leadership style build trust and foster connectivity among their employees and their organization [21]. To improve the organization's commitment, transformational leaders “inspire the follower motivation of achievement and a higher hierarchy of need in order to strengthen the organizational commitment” [22].

Researchers have discovered the influence of leadership styles on teachers' organizational commitment in different situations. For example, Shila and Sevilla [23] found that Indian teachers were shown to be more satisfied with their jobs, and committed to the organization if they had access to transformational leadership. Wahab *et al.* [24] conducted a study on the job satisfaction and dedication of Malaysian primary school teachers and the relationship between these attributes and the transformational leadership of school principals. Teacher dedication to their profession is clearly connected with the level of transformational leadership. In order to boost their employees' satisfaction and commitment, researchers recommend that leaders ensure their high performance leadership. In addition, Aydin, Sarier, and Uysal [25] also investigated the link between transformational leadership and organizational commitment. The results showed that principals’ transformational leadership style positively affected job satisfaction and organizational commitment of teachers. It was concluded that as the leadership style of principal’s changes from transactional to transformational, the level of job satisfaction and organizational commitment of teachers improves. According to Zeleke and Yeshitila [26], transformational leadership behaviors influenced employees’ willingness to commit to their jobs.

The findings of the previous studies were supported by some recent studies which reported that transformational leadership rather than transactional leadership has a greater impact on teachers' job happiness, organizational commitment, and overall school success [27]–[29]. For example, Noraazian and Khalip [27] conducted a study on the organizational commitment of Malaysian primary school teachers and the relationship between this attribute and the transformational leadership of school principals. The results showed that teachers' organizational commitment is clearly connected with the level of transformational leadership. In order to boost their teachers' commitment, researchers recommend that principals ensure their high transformational leadership. Another study conducted in Greece found that teachers showed considerable commitment to school goals when the school principals acted as transformational leaders [29]. Other studies have shown that school leaders with a transformational leadership style empower teachers to recognize that they play a crucial role in the schools [30]–[33]. As a result, highly motivated and dedicated teachers lead to better results, greater commitment, and greater satisfaction in the work. Teachers' work commitment and dedication to the school were positively correlated with leaders' transformational leadership style, whereas teachers' burnout was negatively related with it [9], [34], [35].

The literature review shows that the transformational and transactional leadership styles have significant influences on teachers' organizational commitment. Although the effect of these leadership styles on teachers' organizational commitment has been widely researched in other countries, only a few small-scale studies [1], [6], [11] from Vietnam have examined the effects of socio-cultural factors on leadership styles and the relationship between principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction. No study has investigated the effects of leadership styles on teachers' organizational commitment in the Vietnamese educational context. Therefore, this study aims to explore how transformational and transactional leadership styles of principals influence the level of organizational commitment among teachers in Vietnamese public high schools. In addition, this research seeks to determine whether or not principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles predict teachers' organizational commitment. The following hypotheses are investigated in the present study: Teachers' organizational commitment is influenced by principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles (H1) and teachers' organizational commitment is predicted by principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles (H2).

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Participants

In this study, 387 classroom teachers (grades 10-12) from 24 junior high schools in Vietnam were selected as a convenience sample; there were 195 females (50.40%) and 192 males (49.60%). Participants had a mean teaching experience of 13.64 years ($SD=7.03$) and an average age of 38.27 years ($SD=10.85$). Researchers were able to recruit all 387 teachers from 24 high schools after securing authorization from the school administrations. Participants received thorough descriptions of the research and were informed that they might leave the study at any time. The participant identities and other identifying details were kept confidential. There were two surveys given to participants at the beginning of the second semester of the academic year. Researchers received completed questionnaires from teachers who had participated in the study.

2.2. Instruments

2.2.1. Multifactor leadership questionnaire

Bass and Avolio [36] developed a questionnaire with 45 items to measure nine different aspects of leadership, including transformational leadership, and transactional leadership, and three different outcomes of leadership: increased effort, increased effectiveness, and increased happiness. When it comes to leadership styles, just 36 questions were used in this research. The transformational leadership style includes 5 components: IIa (e.g., "Acts in ways that builds my respect"), IIb (e.g., "Specifies the importance of having a strong sense of purpose"), IM (e.g., "Talks enthusiastically about what needs to be accomplished"), IS (e.g., "Re-examines critical assumptions to question whether they are appropriate"), and IC (e.g., "Spends time teaching and coaching"). The transactional leadership style consists of 4 components: CR (e.g., "Discusses in specific terms who is responsible for achieving performance targets"), AmbE (e.g., "Concentrates his/her full attention on dealing with mistakes, complaints, and failures"), MbEP (e.g., "Waits for things to go wrong before taking action"), and LF (e.g., "Avoids getting involved when important issues arise"). Each component consisted of 4 items and was answered on a scale between 1 (not at all) and 5 (frequently) points. The mean, standard deviations and alpha coefficient of this questionnaire are listed in Table 1.

2.2.2. Organizational commitment scale

Allen and Meyer [17] developed a questionnaire with 24 items to assess three aspects of organizational commitment of teachers. Organizational commitment includes three components: AC (e.g., "I

enjoy discussing my organization with people outside it”), CC (e.g., “I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization”), and NC (e.g., “I was taught to believe in the value of remaining loyal to one’s organization”). Each component consisting of eight items was answered on a scale between 1 (strongly disagree) and 5 (strongly agree) points. The mean, standard deviations, and alpha coefficient of the scale are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive data of independent and dependent variables (n=387)

Variables		Mean (M)	Standard deviations (SD)	Alpha (α)	No. Items
Independent	Transformational leadership				
	IIa	3.90	0.66	0.84	4
	IIb	3.83	0.74	0.81	4
	IM	3.82	0.81	0.89	4
	IS	3.66	0.57	0.76	4
	IC	3.65	0.49	0.79	4
	Transactional leadership				
	CR	3.83	0.81	0.87	4
	AMbE	2.09	0.66	0.77	4
	MbEP	2.16	0.74	0.83	4
	LF	2.33	0.57	0.79	4
Dependent	Organizational commitment				
	AC	3.88	0.55	0.81	8
	CC	3.89	0.55	0.77	8
	NC	3.55	0.50	0.79	8

2.3. Data analyses

Both survey instruments yielded descriptive and inferential data, which were combined and evaluated. The correlation coefficients analyses were employed to investigate the connections between independent variables (nine components of transformational and transactional leadership styles) and dependent variables (three components of organizational commitment). The multiple regression analyses were also performed to see if there was any correlation between independent variables (predictor variables) and dependent variables (outcome variables). All tests were conducted with a significance level of $p < 0.05$, which is the least level of significance required.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Relationship between leadership styles and teachers’ organizational commitment

According to Pearson's correlation coefficients shown in Table 2, the bivariate correlations between the three organizational commitment factors and the nine leadership style characteristics were statistically significant at the 0.01 level. For all five elements of the transformational leadership style, there was a positive association between AC (r ranged from 0.27 to 0.72), CC (r ranged from 0.28 to 0.73), and NC (r ranged from 0.44 to 0.72). One of the four components of the transactional leadership style, CR, showed positive correlational associations with AC (0.27), CC (0.28), and NC (0.45), while the other three components, AmbE, MbEP, and LF, had adverse correlational associations with AC (-.68, -.72, and -.27, respectively), with CC (-.68, -.73, and -.28, respectively), and with NC (-.50, -.52, and -.45, respectively).

Table 2. Correlational matrix between leadership styles and organizational commitment (n=353)

Leadership styles	Organizational commitment		
	AC	CC	NC
IIa	0.68**	0.69**	0.50**
IIb	0.72**	0.73**	0.53**
IM	0.71**	0.70**	0.44**
IS	0.27**	0.28**	0.45**
IC	0.31**	0.33**	0.72**
CR	0.27**	0.28**	0.45**
AmbE	-.68**	-.68**	-.50**
MbEP	-.72**	-.73**	-.52**
LF	-.27**	-.28**	-.45**

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

3.1.2. Predicting teachers’ organizational commitment from leadership styles

Three regression analyses for the five transformational leadership style traits in predicting teachers’ organizational commitment are shown in Table 3. The results indicated that teachers’ organizational commitment was predicted by all five facets of the transformational leadership style. The models explained 62% of the variance in NC ($R^2=0.64$, $F=138.99$, and $p<0.001$), 62% of the variance in CC ($R^2=0.62$, $F=128.33$, and $p<0.001$), and 59% of the variance in AC ($R^2=0.59$, $F=112.93$, $p<0.001$). Table 4 shows that all five elements of the transformational leadership style, including the beta values of Ila (β ranged from 0.13 to 0.24), I Ib (β ranged from 0.14 to 0.38), IM (β ranged from 0.12 to 0.31), IS (β ranged from 0.12 to 30), and IC (β ranged from 0.13 to 0.55), were found to be positively and statistically significant correlated with AC, CC and NC. Teachers’ organizational commitment was most strongly predicted by the I Ib, whereas the I Ia was the weakest indicator of that commitment.

Table 3. Multiple regression analyses on transformational leadership and organizational commitment

	Model 1 (AC)			Model 2 (CC)			Model 3 (NC)		
	R ²	F	p	R ²	F	p	R ²	F	p
	0.59	112.93	.000	0.62	128.33	.000	0.64	138.99	.000

*p < .05; **p < .01

Dependent variables: AC=affektive commitment, CC=continuance commitment, NC=normative commitment

Table 4. Transformational leadership predicted organizational commitment

Variable	Model 1 (AC)			Model 2 (CC)			Model 3 (NC)		
	β	t	p	β	t	p	β	t	p
I Ia	0.17	1.87	.049	0.13	2.06	.039	0.24	4.04	.000
I Ib	0.35	6.23	.000	0.38	6.98	.000	0.14	3.50	.000
IM	0.31	4.44	.000	0.30	4.51	.000	0.12	3.15	.004
IS	0.28	6.94	.000	0.30	7.58	.000	0.12	3.21	.001
IC	0.29	6.97	.000	0.13	2.12	.035	0.55	13.79	.000

Dependent variables: AC=affektive commitment, CC=continuance commitment, NC=normative commitment

Predictors: I Ia=idealized influence attributed, I Ib=idealized influence behavior, IM=inspirational motivation, IS=intellectual stimulation, IC=individualized consideration

For the purpose of predicting teachers’ organizational commitment based on four transactional leadership style attributes, three multiple regression analyses were conducted as presented in Table 5. The four traits of the transactional leadership style were shown to be responsible for 64% of the variance in AC ($R^2=0.64$; $F=178.45$; $p<0.001$), 60% of the variance in CC ($R^2=0.65$; $F=176.35$; $p<0.001$), and 47% of the variance in NC ($R^2=0.47$; $F=84.88$; $p<0.001$). Table 6 shows that three components of transactional leadership were negatively significant associated with the three aspects of organizational commitment, with the beta values of AmbE (β ranged from -.11 to -.26), MbEP (β ranged from -.23 to -.32), and LF (β ranged from -.26 to -.42). In terms of organizational commitment, the only CR component (β ranged from 0.17 to 0.37) was shown to be positively and statistically significant. The results indicated all four components of transactional leadership predicted teachers' organizational commitment. In these components, the weakest predictor of organizational commitment was the AmbE, while the LF was the strongest.

Table 5. Multiple regression analyses on transactional leadership and organizational commitment

	Model 4 (AC)			Model 5 (CC)			Model 6 (NC)		
	R ²	F	p	R ²	F	p	R ²	F	p
	0.64	178.45	.000	0.65	176.35	.000	0.47	84.88	.000

*p < .05; **p < .01

Table 6. Transactional leadership predicted organizational commitment

Variable	Model 4 (AC)			Model 5 (CC)			Model 6 (NC)		
	β	t	p	β	t	p	β	t	p
CR	0.37	5.66	.000	0.37	5.60	.000	0.17	2.83	.040
AmbE	-.12	-2.03	.042	-.11	-1.90	.047	-.26	-3.48	.001
MbEP	-.31	-6.17	.000	-.32	-6.24	.000	-.23	-3.61	.000
LF	-.26	-8.36	.000	-.26	-8.38	.000	-.42	-10.95	.000

Predictors: CR=contingent reward, AmbE=active management by exception), MbEP=management by exception passive, LF=laissez-faire leadership

3.2. Discussion

The present study aims to examine the relationship between principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles and teachers' organizational commitment as well as the degree to which these leadership styles predict teachers' commitment to their organization. The results of correlation coefficient analyses confirmed the first hypothesis that principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles influenced teachers' organizational commitment. Both transformational and transactional leadership styles were shown to have significant effects on teachers' organizational commitment. Transformational leadership style components and one transactional leadership style component (contingent incentive) had significantly positive impacts on teachers' organizational commitment, whereas transactional leadership style components had significantly negative effects.

Five behaviors of transformational leadership style (i.e., idealized influence attributed, idealized influence behavior, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration), and one transactional leadership behavior (contingent reward) exhibited significantly positive correlations with teachers' organizational commitment. Specifically, higher levels of organizational commitment and less transactional leadership traits (active management by exception, management by exception passive, and laissez-faire leadership) were associated with teachers' assessments of their principal's transformational leadership. The results of the present study showed that teacher commitment to their schools was higher among those who agreed with their principals on the transformational leadership style and the contingent reward of the transactional leadership practices. The findings of this study supported those of earlier research [23]–[26], [30]–[33] in which the transformational principal leadership style positively influenced the level of teachers' organizational commitment. Additionally, the findings revealed that teachers' organizational commitment was negatively influenced by the transactional leadership style of principals, except for the contingent reward component, as found in other studies [22], [25], [28], [30].

When it comes to teachers' organizational commitment, transformational leadership has a significant effect. Because of the favorable impact of transformational leaders on their employees, this conclusion was comprehensible. Leaders that are transformational act as role models for their staff by upholding high ethical and behavioral standards [8]. These leaders inspire people to go above and beyond expectations, encourage employees to think on their own, and help them enhance their problem-solving abilities [9], [35]. As a result of transformational leadership, leaders regard their subordinates as individuals and encourage them by finding their particular abilities [1].

The findings of the present study showed that transformational leadership was found to be preferred by Vietnamese teachers over transactional leadership. Specifically, teachers do not want a principal who often rewards good behaviors and punishes bad behaviors, oversees and monitors performance and makes a note of mistakes, and fails to act or judge promptly when serious problems occur [5]. The findings indicated that the three components of organizational commitment are influenced by both transformational and transactional leadership variables, although the size and direction of their effect varies. Despite the similarities between transactional and transformational leadership, prior research has indicated that transformational leaders' actions have a higher favorable influence on teachers' outcomes, including their job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior [3], [4].

This study indicated a positive correlation between teachers' organizational commitment and the transactional leadership's contingent reward component was found. This may be because, in Vietnamese high schools, principals play a critical role in rewarding teachers with dependent advantages like money, promotions, and prestige in order to acknowledge individual teachers' accomplishments. The three transactional leadership characteristics of active management by exception, management by exception passive, and laissez-faire leadership had a negative effect on teacher commitment. Previous research [8], [35] found that passive-avoidance leadership (i.e., management by exception passive, and laissez-faire leadership behaviors) negatively connected to teacher commitment. Transactional leaders were viewed by their followers as ineffective, and this conduct was counterproductive in enhancing their drive [5], [10].

The results of multiple regression analyses also confirmed the second hypothesis that both transformational and transactional leadership styles predicted teachers' organizational commitment. This finding was in line with some previous studies [7], [8], [20], [22], [23], [25], which indicated that teachers' organizational commitment was predicted by actions of transformational and transactional leaders. The present study confirmed universal features of leadership styles across different societies documented by Bass [14] despite the differences in the culture of Vietnam and other countries. The present study showed that teacher organizational commitment may be improved by emphasizing transformational leadership style components. In this study, teachers' commitment is higher when principals embrace more transformational leadership style and more contingent incentive dimension of transactional leaders. Due to these influences on their teachers, principals are more likely to demonstrate transformational leadership traits like the idealized influence attributed (do exemplary role model for teachers), the idealized influence behavior (own the highest

moral and ethical standards while creating an inclusive mission and vision for their team), the inspirational motivation (inspire followers by providing examples, communicating a shared vision, and establishing commitment from her or his followers in achieving the goals set by the organization), the intellectual stimulation (challenge their followers' ideas and values for solving problems, and the individualized consideration (provide a supportive environment for teaching, coaching and developing new followers [8].

Both transformational and transactional leadership paradigms are common in all societies and communities [13]. According to the results of this research, transformational leadership also has a significant influence on high school teachers' organizational commitment in Vietnam. This might be a valuable resource for leaders who want to learn more about transformational leadership and how it can improve their own effectiveness as well as the performance of their organizations. For this reason, educational administrators in Vietnam should be aware of and adopt actions associated with a transformational leadership style in order to create better levels of organizational leadership among teachers. For effective leadership, school leaders need to combine both transformational and transactional leadership traits.

As stated Sun, Chen, and Zhang [10], effective school leaders have been found to have a blend of both transformational and transactional leadership styles. Leaders that practice transformational leadership foster the growth of their subordinates, push them to think beyond the box, and encourage their teams to go above and beyond their previous expectations by staying focused on the core principles and high moral standards that serve as their compass [8]. The transactional contingent reward leadership establishes relationships between leaders and subordinates by setting expectations, describing tasks and rewards for meeting or exceeding those expectations [5]. Thus, the present study strengthens the application of the transformational leadership style and the contingent reward component of the transactional leadership style in the Vietnamese educational context. The transformational leadership may also be a central component of training programs for teachers as well as development programs for school principals in Vietnam to help them practice this leadership style to improve teachers' organizational commitment.

4. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between teachers' organizational commitment and principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles, as well as the degree to which these leadership styles may predict teachers' organizational commitment in Vietnam. All aspects of transformational and transactional leadership styles were, except for the active management by exception, management by exception passive, and laissez-faire leadership characteristics, shown to have a significant and positive effect on teachers' commitment to their organizations. In addition, both transformational and transactional leadership styles significantly predicted teachers' commitment to their organizations. It was shown that teachers were more dedicated to their profession when they believed their leaders had more idealized influence attributed, idealized influence behavior, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration behaviors. Higher levels of active management by exception, management by exception passive, and laissez-faire leadership behaviors were associated with lower levels of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment in teachers. This study offers a better understanding of significant impacts of transformational leadership on the organizational commitment of Vietnamese high school teachers.

In spite of the fact that this study found strong connections between transformational and transactional leadership and teachers' organizational commitment, there are several limitations to this research. Firstly, the study used a non-probability sampling technique with only 387 teachers as a sample size. To have a complete picture of all teachers across the country and to be able to generalize the findings, thus, future research should use random samples with a bigger sample size. Secondly, only two types of leadership were examined in this study, which limited the scope of our investigation. Therefore, the impacts of transactional and transformational leadership styles on teachers' perceptions of their self-efficacy, motivation, performance, and their job satisfaction should be examined. In addition, a follow-up research may explore the effect of transformational leadership on other teachers' outcomes in Vietnam in order to confirm the findings of the present study that transformational and transactional leadership are universally applicable across cultural contexts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is funded by Vietnam National University Ho Chi Minh City (VNU-HCM) under grant number "C2022-16-07".

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